

Barley's gluten challenge: A path to hordein-free food and malt

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ABSTRACT

Barley, a vital cereal crop worldwide, is hindered by hordeins, gluten proteins triggering adverse reactions in those with celiac disease (CeD) and non-celiac gluten sensitivity (NCGS). Recent barley breeding advancements focus on creating varieties with reduced hordein content. Researchers have developed ultra-low gluten barley mutants via targeted genetic modifications, showing significantly decreased hordein levels, potentially safe for CeD and NCGS individuals. However, some mutants carry undesirable traits, which are addressed through further breeding and new genomic techniques. These innovative methods offer promising ways to eliminate unwanted traits and transfer the ultra-low gluten characteristic to diverse barley cultivars, expanding dietary choices and potentially transforming the food and beverage industry with gluten-free barley-based products. This review addresses hordeins' impact and ultra-low gluten barley development and proposes using new genomic techniques for safe barley lines.

1. Barley, hordeins and the gluten challenge

Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* subsp. *vulgare* (L.) K. Richt) is the 4th highest-produced cereal crop in the world, behind wheat, rice, and maize, with a production of over 154 million tons in 2022 (FAOSTAT, 2022). Out of all barley harvested, over 50 % is used for animal feed, 40% for malt and only 0.5 % for food supply (FAOSTAT, 2022). Historically, barley as food has been known from early neolithic times, roughly 10,000 BP, and is still a staple food in some regions (Lukinac and Jukic, 2022). Health benefits are various, either by providing minerals and vitamins or health-beneficial dietary fibre, which helps with, for example, weight loss, insulin resistance and cholesterol levels (Farg et al., 2022; Zhang et al., 2023). Using barley with probiotic food supplements is also possible, and research shows promising health-beneficial effects (Sharma et al., 2022). Barley grains have a broad spectrum of protein content between 8% and 30 %, which could be affected by genetic and environmental factors, especially nitrogen uptake. The total protein content is a crucial trait in breeding for malting and feed (Kumar et al., 2023). A higher protein content is preferable if barley is used for feed, whereas in malting, a specific content between 10 and 12 % is expected (Izydorczyk and Edney, 2017). Two main fractions of proteins found in barley grains comprise 95% of total proteins – hordeins and glutelin (Shewry and Halford, 2002). Hordeins are categorised as prolamins because of their high proline and glutamine amino

acid content. They are the most similar to wheat gluten proteins and lead to allergic reactions in people with coeliac disease (CeD) or non-celiac disease gluten sensitivity (NCGS) (Rubin and Crowe, 2020). The symptoms of CeD and NCGS diseases can be similar but have a broad spectrum of intensity and lifelong effects (Rubin and Crowe, 2020). It is essential to understand that the symptoms and medical conditions caused by CeD harbour potential long-term health consequences, with severe consequences for the patient (Rej et al., 2020; Rubin and Crowe, 2020). It is estimated that between 5% and 14% of people are suffering from an NCGS (Aziz et al., 2014; Jansson-Knodell et al., 2023), while 0.77% globally suffer from CeD (Bradauskiene et al., 2023). The primary genetic predispositions with the highest probability for CeD are HLA-DQ2 and HLA-DQ8 (Abadie et al., 2024; Rubin and Crowe, 2020). In most cases, the HLA-DQ2 loci are present with the formation of HLA-DQ2.5, resulting in a stronger binding to deamidated gluten peptides (Abadie et al., 2024; Rubin and Crowe, 2020). The only current treatment for CeD and NCGS is a gluten-free diet. TCR-like antibodies and other therapeutic approaches are being explored for CeD treatment. (Camarca et al., 2023; Noori et al., 2024; Okura et al., 2023). In this review, we want to give a brief overview of hordeins and their implications for people with CeD and NCGS, as well as how breeding with the aid of new genomic techniques is trying to introduce quality-of-life traits.

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2. Hordeins – the gluten of barley

2.1. Hordeins – the classification of the barley gluten

The term gluten incorporates an enormous family of proteins, which all share similarities and are named after the species they originate from. Gluten translates from the Latin word for glue due to its properties. It was Thomas Burr Osborne in 1907, who was the first to describe that gluten is composed of different proteins, glutenins and gliadins (This, 2018). In barley, they are called hordeins (Shewry and Halford, 2002). The barley hordeins are a family of proteins consisting of four closely related members: B-, C-, D-, and γ -hordeins (P. Shewry et al., 1980).

Phylogenetic analysis of prolamins in family of Poaceae shown fascinating way of evolution among them. The most ancient gene seems to be HMW glutenin from wheat. Most probable is that water-insoluble storage proteins (prolamins) likely evolved from water-soluble ones (α -globulins), which happen through duplication of chromosomal regions. After non-homologous pairing of chromosomal regions, followed by duplication and insertion into different chromosomal locations, that lead to other types of prolamins, donor copy of HMW glutenin was lost in *Ehrhartoideae* and *Panicoideae* subfamilies, and gene remained in its original position next to the globulin gene in *Pooideae* (Xu and Messing, 2009).

Hordeins form about 37% of the total protein in grain (Shewry and Halford, 2002). Evolutionarily, these proteins might be acquired by

grains mainly for reproduction purposes. They give structure for the endosperm development, constitute significant nitrogen storage, and support germination with the uptake of water (Shewry, 2019). Prolamins are enriched in glutamine, proline, histidine and glycine (Shewry and Halford, 2002). During the development of the seed, prolamins are deposited into organelles called protein bodies that are organised and bound to starch granules. During the maturation of the grain, protein bodies disappear, forming a matrix with starch granules (Roustan et al., 2020). For some time, it was suspected that another physiological function of prolamins could be the binding of zinc (Zn), as they show similar motifs as other Zn-related proteins. Zn has an affinity for forming ligands with histidine, glutamate and cysteine, which are abundant in prolamins (Maret, 2005). Fertilisation with Zn shows that it has a positive correlation with the amount of proteins in grains (Uddin, Kaczmarczyk, et al., 2014). However, staining for Zn in gel-separated prolamins fractions showed that only B-hordeins are binding to Zn (Uddin, Nielsen, et al., 2014).

2.2. The B-hordeins

The B-hordeins are sulfur-rich prolamins, having a size of 50 kDa, which can be further categorised into the B1- and B-3 subgroups (M Kreis, S Rahman et al., 1983). Newer studies suggest that the B-hordeins have eleven subgroups (Anderson, 2013). However, only the subgroups B3, B4, B8 and B10 show a high abundance, while the other variants are

Fig. 1. Sunburst diagram of identified hordein peptides connected to CeD: The colour shows grouping based on the hordein class. DQ2 refers to the immune receptor HLA-DQ2, while TG2 refers to transglutaminase 2, an enzyme involved in CeD and gluten deamidation. The peptide information are based on the literature cited and can be found in the supplement (Supplement Table I) (Amnuaycheewa et al., 2022; Freddy et al., 2022; Hardy et al., 2015; Koning et al., 2005; Lexhaller et al., 2020; Picariello et al., 2011; Tok et al., 2021; Tye-Din et al., 2010; Vader et al., 2003).

only detected in limited numbers (Anderson, 2013). Structure-wise, the B-hordeins are similar to the low-molecular-weight (LMW) glutenin from wheat (Anderson, 2013; Han et al., 2010). Recent modelling shows the highest similarity of B-hordein to the wheat α -gliadin (Hajjari and Sharif, 2024) (Fig. 2). This remains true for the wild relative of cultivated barley, *Hordeum chilense* (Pistón et al., 2005). The general structure of B-hordeins follows the wheat LMW-glutenin structure; a signal peptide is followed by a repetitive region, which then is followed by three distinct regions: a non-repetitive domain high in sulfur, a glutamine-rich region and a c-terminal repetitive domain (Anderson, 2013; Han et al., 2010; Pistón et al., 2005; Schalk et al., 2017; Scherf, 2023). We could identify 20 B-hordein peptides connected to CeD, from which 19 are connected to the HLA-DQ2 receptor and one to the transglutaminase2 (TG2) (Fig. 1, Supplement Table 1).

2.3. The C-hordeins

The C-hordeins are often called the S-poor prolamins of barley and account for about 10–20% of the total prolamins (Tatham and Shewry, 2012). The amino acid composition of C-hordeins shows a high abundance of glutamine, proline and phenylalanine (Tatham and Shewry, 2012). Structure-wise, the C-hordeins share a similarity to the ω -gliadins of wheat (Hajjari and Sharif, 2024; Tatham and Shewry, 2012). The typical structure of C-hordeins and their homologues is a worm- or spiral-like structure (Hajjari and Sharif, 2024; Tatham and Shewry, 2012). A critical attribute of C-hordeins is an octapeptide (PQQPFPQQ), one motif involved in the CeD due to its activating function on T-cells (Tatham and Shewry, 2012). C-Hordeins in breadmaking are responsible for the loaf volume, while increasing their content leads to decreasing loaf volume, indicating a similar role as the gliadins in wheat (Tatham and Shewry, 2012). In CeD research, C-hordeins comprise the bulk of the identified peptides connected to CeD (65 peptides) and the HLA-DQ2 receptor (Fig. 1, Supplement Table 1).

2.4. The D-hordeins

D-hordeins account only for a fraction of the hordeins in barley; they have a size of ~100 kDa and can be compared to the high-molecular-weight subunits of glutenin (HMW-GS) (Balakireva and Zamyatnin, 2016; Hajjari and Sharif, 2024; Schalk et al., 2017; Vinje et al., 2019). Their modelled structure is rod-like, similar to the C-hordeins, γ - or ω -gliadins (Hajjari and Sharif, 2024). They further share some

similarities with B-hordeins, mainly the peptide motif (LQPHQIAQL), and immunological analysis of beer shows the prevalence of these peptides, together with the C-hordein peptides in beer and their complications for CeD- or NCGS-patients (Picariello et al., 2011). D-hordeins are the smallest group of hordeins found in our literature search, with only 5 individual peptides identified (Fig. 1, Supplement Table 1). These 5 peptides were also recently discovered in connection with TG2 and, therefore, are not directly linked to CeD.

2.5. The γ -hordeins

The last member of the hordein family is γ -hordein. They have a mass of 33 kDa and, similar to B-hordeins, are sulfur-rich (Scherf, 2023). Structure-wise, they share high similarities with the γ -gliadins of wheat; the difference to B-hordeins or α -gliadins is the absence of the highly repetitive region (Scherf, 2023). Their structure, based on modelling, resembles similarities to a worm-like structure (Hajjari and Sharif, 2024). Interestingly, only the γ - and B-hordeins are posttranslational glycosylated or glycosylated, while the other hordeins are only glycosylated, showing their similarities to LMW-glutenins (Bobalova et al., 2023). The γ -hordeins are the third biggest group according to our data of identified peptides (Supplement Table 1), with a total of 13 identified peptides, which are divided into two groups (Fig. 1). The majority of peptides are directly associated with the HLA-DQ2 receptor (Fig. 1). In contrast, a third is identified as binding to TG2 (Fig. 1).

2.6. Hordein peptides

Since the breakdown of hordeins into peptides is essential in the CeD pathway, researchers have identified many peptides of barley hordeins associated with CeD. In our literature search, we could identify 105 hordein peptides (Fig. 1, Supplement Table 1).

When the details of these 105 hordein peptide sequences are examined, they can be classified into four major groups (Supplement Fig. 1). Group I – QPQQPFP(L/Q/W); Group II – PQQPGQ(G/W)Q; Group III – Q(Q/P)FPQPQP(F/I)(P/R/S) and Group IV – F(S/Q/P)P(I/Y/V/F)PQQPQ(Y/F). Some exciting aspects arise when grouping hordeins and the peptide groups (Fig. 1). The B-hordeins only contain peptides from groups I and IV, and group IV represents 85% of the peptides of the B-hordeins (Fig. 1). For the C-hordeins, groups I, III and IV are present with nearly equal share (Fig. 1). At the same time, all three groups are also connected to γ -hordeins. However, with a different distribution (Fig. 1).

Fig. 2. Proteins folding structure of (A) barley and (b) wheat, with schematic domain structure, showing repeated motifs in repeat domain (RD, grey) and low repeat domain ($_{low}$ RD, light grey) in γ -hordeins: Haplotypes of CeD patients reacting to specific proteins are shown as receptors HLA-DQ 2.2 (light grey), HLA-DQ 2.5 (grey), HLA-DQ 8 (orange), and HLA-DQ 8.5 (red). Protein structure prediction from (Hajjari and Sharif, 2024) and UniProt database.

Group II is only found in connection with D-hordein peptides. They make up 80% of the peptides associated with D-hordeins.

3. Removing hordeins through traditional breeding: are we ready for celiac-safe products?

3.1. Genetic background in barley

The four barley hordeins B-, C-, D-, and γ -Hordein are all encoded in large complex multiple gene clusters (M Kreis, PR Shewry et al., 1983; P. Shewry et al., 1985; Shewry and Halford, 2002). These gene clusters can be further classified into different families based on the polymorphism of the proteins encoded by them (Pomortsev et al., 2021). It is currently believed that these polymorphisms are caused by two phenomena: The spontaneous hybridisation between cultivated barley and its wild progenitor and the accumulation of mutations in the gene loci (Pomortsev et al., 2021). Comparison of wild barley and cultivated barley hordein structures shed further light on the history of hordein polymorphism, revealing similarities of 10–14 % between wild barley and cultivated barley (Pomortsev et al., 2022).

B-Hordeins were believed to be encoded by 13 genes at the Hor2 locus, located on the short arm of chromosome 1H (Fig. 3) (M Kreis, S Rahman et al., 1983; M Kreis, PR Shewry et al., 1983). At least in cultivar Barke, expression analysis gives further insight into the Hor2 locus. Evidence indicates only nine full-length genes, one tentative full-length gene, a truncated B-hordein and two or three pseudogenes (Anderson, 2013). Among these genes, only four unique sequences

represent 83% of the detected ESTs (Anderson, 2013). A recent comparison between two barley accessions, cv. Bowman and GSHO 2096 further indicated that a deletion of 85 kbp to 1.2 Mbp leads to the elimination of the Hor2 locus, thus the absence of B-hordein gene expression and B-hordein protein from the Hor2 locus (Gregory J. Tanner et al., 2016; Vinje et al., 2024). Proteome analysis of these knock-out cultivars showed that there are still B-hordeins present, which led to the identification of a second locus, closer to the centromere of chromosome 1H, harbouring at least 2 B-hordein genes (Fig. 3) (Bose et al., 2021).

The C-hordeins, the primary classes of hordeins, are also located on the short arm of chromosome 1H at the Hor1 locus (Fig. 3) (P. Shewry et al., 1985; Shewry and Halford, 2002). The Hor1 locus consists of 20–30 genes, with a size of 105–190 kb and many polymorphisms (Michalek et al., 1997; Pomortsev et al., 2021; P. Shewry et al., 1985; Siedler and Graner, 1991). Fluorescence in situ hybridisation of the Hor1 and Hor2 loci revealed a distance of 13 cM between them, which is in line with the average distance between both loci in different crosses (Pedersen and Linde-Laursen, 1995). Like the B-hordein loci Hor2 and Hor2b, the C-hordeins have an additional locus. The second Hor1 locus, Hor1b, is also on chromosome 1H but more to the centromeric region, separated by 0.7 Mbp to the Hor2b locus and containing two additional C-hordein genes (Fig. 3) (Bose et al., 2021).

Oposed to the other two members of the hordein family, the locus for D-hordein is not located on the short arm of chromosome 1H but on the long arm at the centromere region (Fig. 3) (Blake et al., 1982; Shewry et al., 1983). Distance-wise, Hor3 lies 9 cM from the centromere

Fig. 3. Schematic overview of chromosome 1H of barley and the location of the hordein loci, its structure and an indication of first discovered mutants.

and 30 cM from the Hor1 locus (Blake et al., 1982; Shewry et al., 1983). Another difference between Hor1, Hor2 and Hor3 is the locus structure. The Hor3 locus is 120 kbp long, contains four genes separated by transposons and is highly conserved (Gu et al., 2003). Comparisons to the wheat HMW-glutenin locus indicate the ancestry between both, with a duplication in the wheat genome leading to a further classification (Gu et al., 2003). However, only one gene in the Hor3 locus is responsible for D-hordeins' expression, as confirmed by knock-out mutants (Gu et al., 2003; Yang et al., 2020).

Evidence for the γ -hordeins was found in the B-hordein deletion mutant Risø56, which enabled the identification of γ -hordein (P. R. Shewry et al., 1985). Since then, two genes were identified at the Hor 5 locus, corresponding to three proteins (Cameron-Mills and Brandt, 1988; Shewry & Parmar, 1987; P. R. Shewry et al., 1985), later it was shown there are 3 genes and 2 proteins expressed (Bose et al., 2021). The location of Hor5 is, like Hor1 and Hor2, on chromosome 1H, more detailed on the short arm of chromosome 1H, tightly linked to the B-hordein loci (Fig. 3) (Shewry & Parmar, 1987; P. R. Shewry et al., 1985). One might believe, due to the tight co-location of Hor2 and Hor5, that both are one locus, but this is not the case. In Hor2 deficient mutants, the expression of two Hor5 mRNAs was still observed (Cameron-Mills and Brandt, 1988).

3.2. The current progress of low-hordein barley breeding

Barley breeding throughout the last century has already achieved the goal of generating mutants deficient in single or multiple hordeins (Table 1). We, therefore, want to give an overview of what has been achieved and the possible development of barley breeding for low glucan content.

3.3. B-hordein

In a search for the higher nutritional value of barley grains used for feed, high lysine mutants were pursued. Among the gamma-ray-radiation-induced mutant collection of the Carlsberg II cultivar, a plant, Risø 56, had a very low abundance of B-hordein. Analysis of the molecular basis of this mutation shows an 85 kb deletion on chromosome 1H, encompassing the Hor2 locus that codes for B-hordeins (M. Kreis et al., 1983). Risø 56 shows a 30% decrease in total hordein

Table 1
Barley mutants with alteration in their hordein content.

Name	Mutation	Background	Protein content	Malting quality	Reference
Risø 56	ΔB	Carlsberg II	10 %	NA	Doll (1980)
Risø 1508	ΔC	Bomi	11.5 %	NA	P. R. Shewry, A. J. Faulks, S. Parmar et al. (1980)
Ethiopian black landrace	ΔD	–	11.6 %	Low, not effected by D-	Brennan et al. (1998)
ULG single mutants	ΔB ΔC ΔD	Sloop	~7 % ~5 % ~12 %	NA	Bose et al. (2020)
ULG double mutants	$\Delta B\Delta C$ $\Delta B\Delta D$ $\Delta C\Delta D$	Sloop	~11.6 % ~8.4 % ~7.7 %	NA	(Bose et al., 2021; Colgrave et al., 2016)
ULG2.0	$\Delta B\Delta C$	–	13.2 %	Medium	(G. J. Tanner et al., 2016)
ULG3.0	$\Delta B\Delta C\Delta D$	Sloop	14.9 %	Medium	Tanner et al., 2016)
ULG3.2	$\Delta B\Delta C\Delta D$	Sloop, Baudin, Yagan	11 %	Medium acceptable	
Ukrainian black ultra-low	Double mutants	Achilles	NA	NA	Rybalka et al. (2021)

accumulation, with D-hordein being unaffected while the C-hordein amount was increased twice, and B-hordein was reduced by over 95% (P. R. Shewry, A. J. Faulks, & B. J. Mifflin, 1980). Unfortunately, these mutants have lowered yield and shrunken kernel phenotype. They were grown in small amounts in Denmark but were never broadly commercialised (Doll, 1980). However, it was used in breeding programs. An example is line GSHO 2096, which is reported to have a high amylase trait (Vinje et al., 2024).

3.4. C-hordein

Another Risø mutant, Risø 1508, which was an effect of EMS-induced mutation, was shown to have a mutation on chromosome 5H that affected the Lys3 locus (Table 1). Lys3 is an encoding transcription factor that activates or represses the transcription of several genes by binding to specific sequences in their promotor regions. It resulted in an almost total reduction of C-hordeins and affected other hordein types. Risø 1508 showed a 20% lower yield than the Bomi cultivar, which it originated from (P. R. Shewry, A. J. Faulks, & B. J. Mifflin, 1980). RNAi targeting C-hordeins was also used to produce a transgenic line that had 45% lower C-hordein content and higher D- and B-hordein by ~2%, which led to changes in other S-rich protein pathways (Hansen et al., 2007; Lange et al., 2007). A recent study in the proteome of the single hordeins null lines showed that mutation in Risø 1508 resulted in a change in abundance of 108 proteins compared to WT plants (Bose et al., 2020).

3.5. D-hordein

In the '90s, a spontaneous mutant in the D-hordein locus was found in the John Innes Centre germplasm collection. The line was a 6-row Ethiopian landrace with black grains. Then Brennan et al. (1998) (Table 1) crossed it with different breeding lines of 2-row, white-grain European barley, thus Developing a population of six pairs of isogenic lines with contrasting alleles at Hor2 and Hor1 loci. Each line had a mirrored line that was different only in the absence or presence of D-hordeins. These lines were used to test for D-hordeins' effect on malting quality and, almost 20 years later, to develop ultra-low-gluten barley. Li et al. (2020) used CRISPR/Cas9 to develop transgenic lines with a mutation in Hor3 loci. They used two different gRNAs targeting the beginning of the D-hordein gene. T1 plants had a 45-bp deletion that led to a frame-shift mutation, resulting in a protein of 167 amino acids, compared to 748 amino acids long WT.

3.6. Double and triple mutants

Using Risø 56, Risø 1508 and black Ethiopian landrace, double mutants were obtained, and their proteome was analysed (Table 1). To remove background differences, all single mutants were crossed with malt cultivar Sloop and backcrossed three times, and then all possible combinations of double mutants were obtained by crossing Sloop-single-nulls (Colgrave et al., 2016). Double mutants still preserved the shrunken phenotype, and the $\Delta B\Delta D$ -mutant was the most similar to WT but still showed changes in the proteome and amino acid composition. $\Delta C\Delta D$ - and $\Delta B\Delta C$ -mutants showed higher content of fatty acids and triacylglycerol, and all three lines showed a significant reduction in starch (between 17% and 31%) and B-glucan content (between 35% and 61%). Double lines also have lower protein content than the WT grains but higher than single mutants. Interestingly, the $\Delta D\Delta B$ -line still showed a similar level of B-hordein as the WT from locus 2 (Bose et al., 2021). The ultra-low gluten (ULG) line was developed by crossing Sloop double mutants $\Delta C\Delta D$ with $\Delta B\Delta C$. Triple mutants do not have B-hordeins from locus Hor2 (Colgrave et al., 2016). Unfortunately, this line still suffered from low yield. However, proteome or other data for this line is not available. Using an adapted strategy, different generations of ULG were developed (Gregory J. Tanner et al., 2016). Researchers from

CSIRO (Australia) combined Risø56 and Risø1508 for the double $\Delta B\Delta C$ -mutant producing ULG2.0 that still contained D-hordein (Table 1), but the total amount of hordeins was decreased by 97% compared to Sloop. The Backcross of the Ethiopian landline with Sloop was used as a component to remove D-hordein from ULG2.0. Obtained grains (ULG3.0) had 44% Sloop background and null allele in all types of hordeins equal to 0.007% of WT Sloop, with only γ -3-hordein present (Table 1). Next, the biparental and triparental intercrossing was used to improve the characteristics of the grains to produce ULG3.2 lines. Compared to three commercial malting cultivars, these lines have similar starch content, total protein content at 11%, and much higher levels of free amino acids. However, all triple lines of ULG3.2 had much lower β -glucan levels (0.5% compared to 3%–4% in control) (G. J. Tanner et al., 2016). Now, ULG was commercialised in Australia under the name Kebari as barley with gluten content under 5 ppm, which qualifies it as gluten-free. Unfortunately, Kebari grains still show a shrunken phenotype and are smaller and thinner than the other malting cultivars. The challenge also lies in the presence of the hull, which poses additional steps in the industrial processing of the grain. Researchers holding patents on Kebari grain are working to develop a hull-less version that could be easier used in functional food products (Howitt et al., 2018). The Ukrainian research group also developed double mutants using Risø and Ethiopian landrace. They aimed to obtain patent-free triple mutants with black grains for high antioxidant activity and hull-less grains for food products. They developed double mutants of Risø56 and Risø1508 ($\Delta B\Delta C$) and backcrossed Ethiopian R118 with Achilles variety, which was characterised by black seeds and no D-hordein (Rybalka et al., 2021). Unfortunately, Kebari took 14 years to develop, so it could be a few more years before we see the ultra-low-gluten barley with dark seeds.

3.7. Hordeins & barley: the consequences of removal

3.7.1. Physiological impact

Prolamins in grains are dominantly supportive of plant germination. As described earlier, they play a significant role in the development of the endosperm, as nitrogen and water storage and a source of amino acids for developing seedlings. The mutation in Risø 56 (ΔB -hordein) led to changes in the kernel compared to Bomi. As previously stated, a side-effect of the mutation in Risø 56 is a higher lysine content. Besides the amino acid composition, the main impact of the mutation was a reduction in kernel weight, which was linked to reduced starch content and shown that it affected starch accumulation but not the composition (Tester et al., 1993). As B-hordein is the main protein in protein bodies, their structure is also affected, leading to abnormal storage deposition and accumulation of the fibrillar component, which is also present in Risø 1508 (Cameron-Mills and Von Wettstein, 1980).

The ΔC -hordein barley Risø 1508 showed severe physiological changes compared to its parent line. The analysis of Risø 1508 revealed a 32% lower dry grain weight than cv. Bomi (Klemsdal et al., 1986). At the same time, the number of nuclei in the endosperm was reduced, which is contradictory since in the same work, it is reported that the amount of starchy cells is equal, while the aleurone cells are reduced in the mutant (Klemsdal et al., 1986). While the cell volume was reduced in the Risø 1508 mutant, and the starch granules were smaller than cv. Bomi, the embryo in Risø 1508 and other *lys3* mutants, was larger (Cook et al., 2018; Klemsdal et al., 1986). At the same time, the lysine content was higher, which had a positive effect on the nutritional value of the grains (Newman et al., 1990). As explained previously, two antisense ΔC -hordein lines were analysed for their protein composition, showing changes in many protein abundance (Lange et al., 2007). Besides the changes to other hordeins, many seed proteins, such as albumins, globulins and glutenins, were upregulated. At the same time, the amino acids more abundant in C-hordein, glutamine, proline and phenylalanine were reduced (Lange et al., 2007). However, no plant physiological analyses were performed, which would enable us to identify whether

lys3 is responsible for some or all of the physiological changes. It is known that in one of the ΔC -hordein antisense lines, upregulation of other hordein genes and proteins is happening (Hansen et al., 2007). B- and C-hordeins fulfil some redundancy since the other hordeins are more prevalent in their respective knock-out lines. It is important to note that these physiological impacts are only in the first generation of hordein lacking lines, and with the generation of ULG3.0 and ULG3.2, the majority of these drawbacks were bred out (Gregory J. Tanner et al., 2016). Making it more likely that the seed phenotypes are linked to the *lys3a* gene introduced by Risø 1508 than the absence of C-hordeins (Gregory J. Tanner et al., 2016).

3.7.2. Beer making quality

There is still a debate in the research community whether malting quality is affected by hordeins or not. Previous research shows that D-hordein hurts malting quality based on different cultivars and seasons (Howard et al., 1996). However, Brennan et al. (1998). Later used isogenic lines show no difference between ΔD and $D+$ plants; they all had relatively poor malting quality. Then Simic et al. (2007) presented data that hordeins can negatively correlate the total hordein content and malt extract yield, with C- and D-hordein having the most prominent influence. However, this research was done on commercial cultivars that also differ in other traits. It was later contested by Prystupa et al. (2019), who noted that the concentration of different hordeins was affected by N and S fertilisation and that environmental conditions affect malt extract more than hordein composition. Some of these contradictory results could be explained by the compromise that D-hordeins significantly affect malting extract, but only when total protein content is below a specific threshold. It is affected similarly by environmental conditions (Otero et al., 2021). No clear relationship exists between composition, B- or C-hordeins amounts, and malting quality. Baxter and Wainwright (1979) observed that out of 16 cultivars, the better malting quality was in the one missing small size B-hordeins and overall lower amount of this type of hordeins. However, just one year later, P. R. Shewry, A. J. Faulks, S. Parmar et al. (1980), in their experiment, saw that winter barleys lacking in low molecular B-hordeins were all poor malting quality when at the same time, in a group of suitable quality cultivars, four of them had presented this type of proteins. Other research also suggested that N fertilisation decreased the proportion of B-hordeins, increased total protein content and reduced malt extract (Prystupa et al., 2021). C-hordeins were also positively affected by N fertilisation. Their relationship to malting quality is more apparent. In most cases, their amount negatively affected malting quality; however, the higher effect was related to the environment (with an observed strict line between south and north European varieties) (Molina-Cano et al., 2000). Comparing two lots of grains from the same cultivar (Scarlett) that differ in malting quality showed that changes in total protein content were related to a higher abundance of C-hordeins (Ferrari et al., 2010). In conclusion, often, when protein content is higher, the quality of malt extract decreases. As the C-hordeins are the second most abundant proteins in grain with a positive correlation of fertilisation, their differences were associated with poor quality traits. Moreover, it is unsurprising that there is such disagreement in the research community, as malting quality is a complex trait with many different factors. The only agreement that could be found is that protein content negatively correlates with malting quality and should be between 10 and 12 %. Double and triple hordein null lines ULG2.0 and ULG3.0 had higher protein content than acceptable in malting cultivars (13.2% and 14.9%), which led to subpar malting properties such as extract %, free amino nitrogen, diastatic power, Kolbach index, the apparent attenuation limit, viscosity and wort β -Glucan content. However, breeding toward improved malting traits resulted in ULG3.2, which had a lower protein content of 11%, which is acceptable in malting grain (G. J. Tanner et al., 2016).

3.7.3. Barley as a functional food

Barley is considered a new functional food as a healthy alternative to

other starchy crops, primarily thanks to dietary fibre - β -glucan content. Barley is known to have a cholesterol-lowering effect and including it in the diet can lead to a lower risk of cardiovascular diseases and diabetes (Raj et al., 2023). However, the baking product from barley cannot compete with one made from wheat (Dhingra and Jood, 2004). It still needs to be understood if it is related to lower and poor gluten networks or other factors. On the other side, noodles or flatbreads made from barley flour are comparable to their wheat equivalents (Zheng et al., 2023), and other dishes made from barley are staples in many countries (Mohammed et al., 2016; Upreti et al., 2005; Verma et al., 2022). Unfortunately, as the use of barley for food is still rare, no studies have been done on the properties of null hordeins lines with this end use in mind. Even though gluten or barley hordeins are the dominant factors for bread making and dough quality, new secondary factors were discovered in barley, which could help in using null hordein flour for baking (Andrzejczak et al., 2024).

4. The future of hordeins: harnessing genomic tools to tailor barley for healthier food and celiac-safe products

4.1. What are NGTs

NGTs refer to a set of techniques used for manipulating the DNA of organisms; they can be broadly categorised into three branches: zinc-finger nucleases (ZFNs), transcription activator-like effector nucleases (TALEN) and oligonucleotide-directed mutagenesis (ODM). Recently, a new addition was published, broadly classified into oligo-directed mutagenesis, using a completely different approach (Durrant et al., 2024; Hiraizumi et al., 2024; Siddiquee et al., 2024). The first two branches, zinc-finger nucleases and transcription activator-like effector nucleases, use the *FokI* endonuclease for DNA cleavage (Gaj et al., 2013). However, both systems have a severe drawback: either the zinc finger or the TALE needs to be specifically designed for the target region, which is a time-consuming and costly process with many limitations (Gaj et al., 2013). The CRISPR/Cas system has evolved to include various modifications to the Cas9 endonuclease, such as the development of nickases, relaxases, and PAM-less variants like SpRY and PhieABE (Ali et al., 2020; Ran et al., 2013; Ren et al., 2021; Tan et al., 2022). These advancements enable more precise genome editing and base conversions without significant disruptions. Prime editing and twin prime editing have been introduced to facilitate specific DNA exchanges and replacements, showing promise in plant genome editing (Lin et al., 2020, 2021). Furthermore, the flexibility of Cas enzymes, such as Cas12 and Cas14a1, allows for targeted cutting and trans-cleavage abilities, making CRISPR/Cas an ideal tool for creating new mutations and designing mutants with desirable traits (Swarts and Jinek, 2019; Wei et al., 2021).

A new genome editing system that can exchange or integrate larger DNA fragments, surpassing the capabilities of CRISPR/Cas, has recently been proposed (Durrant et al., 2024; Hiraizumi et al., 2024; Siddiquee et al., 2024). This new system, called bridgeRNA or seekRNA, is based on bridgeRNA-guided recombination (Durrant et al., 2024; Siddiquee et al., 2024). It leverages transposon elements, DNA fragments capable of moving to new locations in the genome (Hiraizumi et al., 2024). The system utilises a transposase enzyme encoded by transposons, particularly the minimal insertion sequence (IS) elements (Hiraizumi et al., 2024). These transposons could be harnessed to integrate custom-designed DNA into specific locations in the host genome, offering a new tool for researchers and breeders. Unlike CRISPR/Cas, this approach provides the advantage of smaller size and minimal invasion without DNA cleavage or breaking (Durrant et al., 2024; Siddiquee et al., 2024).

4.2. How can we use NGTs to manipulate barley for CeD/NCGS patients?

One drawback of breeding is linkage drag, where the gene of interest (GoI) is linked to an undesired trait (Freddy et al., 2022). Breaking

linkage drag is a time-consuming process that involves several back-crossings and is not always guaranteed to work (Freddy et al., 2022). In the scope of ULG3.2 and barley, two prominent examples would be two resistance genes, *Rrs14* and *Ruhq*, which confer resistance against *Rhynchosporium secalis* and *Ustilago hordei*, respectively (Garvin et al., 2000; Grewal et al., 2004, 2007). *Hor2*, the first discovered B-hordein locus, is closely linked to both genes as a breeding marker (Garvin et al., 2000; Grewal et al., 2004, 2007). *Rrs14*, for example, comes from barley's wild progenitor *Hordeum spontaneum*, and thus, breeding it into cultivated barley lacking the *Hor2* locus would be time-consuming and not guaranteed success (Garvin et al., 2000). In both cases, it might appear more feasible to generate a more precise *Hor2* mutant in lines carrying these resistance genes using NGTs instead of making several crossing attempts due to the linkage and proximity of both to *Hor* loci (Garvin et al., 2000; Grewal et al., 2004). Several possible approaches exist to make a *Hor2* knock-out in the desired background line. One way would be to use CRISPR constructs and multiplexing approaches, cutting out the *Hor2* locus or each gene inside it. Another possibility would be integrating the desired resistance loci into the Risø 56 background, which would be possible using multicopy chromosomal integration (Yang et al., 2021). This approach would also be interesting, using the newly described transposon integration via bridge RNA, which enables large fragments to be integrated (Durrant et al., 2024; Siddiquee et al., 2024). The ULG3.2 is one malting barley cultivar; it took 14 years to introduce it and many more years to transfer it to other cultivars. It would be interesting to test the null hordein barley for food properties in the background, such as highland barley, which has higher β -glucan. This, however, would also transfer negative aspects into the highland barley. Risø 1508, a pedigree of ULG3.2, contains a *lys3a* mutation, which leads to a low β -glucan content, an unwanted trait for food (Benlier et al., 2021; Bose et al., 2021; Schmidt, 2022; Gregory J. Tanner et al., 2016; Zurbau et al., 2021). This low β -glucan content is likely due to two reasons: a down-regulation of a cellulose synthase-like gene *CsLF6* and the significant upregulation of a β -glucanase, an enzyme responsible for β -glucan degradation (Vinje and Simmons, 2024). It is not fully understood why these genes are differentially regulated; while data suggests it is due to the promoter methylation phenotype of the *lys3a* mutants (Vinje and Simmons, 2024), clarification is needed since methylation did not differ between the *lys3a* mutant and the parent in some regions. Using the new NGTs, it could be possible to re-design the promoter region of *CsLF6* or the β -glucanase, increasing the β -glucan content for health-beneficial traits (Benlier et al., 2021; Schmidt, 2022; Tosh and Bordenave, 2020; Zurbau et al., 2021). Proteomic analysis of the single and double mutants in hordein genes showed around 250 proteins affected by the hordein mutations. Most were related to rebalancing metabolic processes when missing hordeins, but some were related to oxidoreductase activity, metal ion binding and starch metabolism (Bose et al., 2021). Plants with a mutation in *lys3* from Risø 1508 show low germination and grown vigour, which may be related to a higher abundance of LEA proteins and changes in transcription factors. It was also demonstrated that Risø 56 has an incomplete deletion of the B-hordeins, passed to the progeny plants. Using precise genome editing techniques would allow the production of new Δ B- and Δ C-hordein mutants with less impairment in other metabolic processes.

5. Conclusions and future development

Barley is an important grain crop for humanity, not only for animal feed but also as a staple food and beer production. One content of barley, the hordein proteins, is gluten protein, infamously known for causing severe symptoms for people with CeD or NCGS. Globally, around 1% and up to 14% are estimated to suffer from CeD and NCGS, respectively. While new medications are in trials, helping people with CeD, the only current therapy is a gluten-free diet. This diet comes with a limited selection of grain-based products incorporating beer. To help people suffering from CeD and NCGS, researchers have recently created an

ultra-low gluten malting cultivar. However, this took over 14 years and is limited to beer-making barley. With the help of NGTs, especially with the introduction of bridgeRNA-based genome-editing, a transfer to other barley cultivars, either malting- or food cultivars, could be accelerated. Additionally, the negative traits introduced in the mutation process could be converted. Patients with CeD should also have access to beneficial health traits related to β -glucan, which can be found in barley, without the risk of consuming gluten. The holy grail for CeD or NCGS patients would be the creation of non-allergenic hordein proteins. This, however, would be an endless endeavour for scientists due to the sheer number of possible epitopes and peptides. We could gather more than 100 peptides linked to CeD (Fig. 1, Supplementary Table 1). Even though many peptides share similarities, which reduces them to four major groups, it might be more feasible to delete the hordeins or look into new therapeutics (Besser and Khosla, 2023; Dieckman et al., 2022; Discepolo et al., 2024).

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Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.plaphy.2024.109174>.

References

- Abadie, V., Han, A.S., Jabri, B., Sollid, L.M., 2024. New insights on genes, gluten, and immunopathogenesis of celiac disease. *Gastroenterology* 167 (1), 4–22. <https://doi.org/10.1053/j.gastro.2024.03.042>.
- Ali, Z., Shami, A., Sedeek, K., Kamel, R., Alhabsi, A., Tehseen, M., Hassan, N., Butt, H., Kababji, A., Hamdan, S.M., Mahfouz, M.M., 2020. Fusion of the Cas9 endonuclease and the VirD2 relaxase facilitates homology-directed repair for precise genome engineering in rice. *Commun. Biol.* 3 (1), 44. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-020-0768-9>.
- Amnuaycheewa, P., Abdelmoteleb, M., Wise, J., Bohle, B., Ferreira, F., Tetteh, A.O., Taylor, S.L., Goodman, R.E., 2022. Development of a sequence searchable database of celiac disease-associated peptides and proteins for risk assessment of novel food proteins. *Frontiers in Allergy* 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/falgy.2022.900573>.

- Anderson, O.D., 2013. The B-hordein prolamin family of barley. *Genome* 56 (3), 179–185. <https://doi.org/10.1139/gen-2013-0016>.
- Andrzejczak, O., Olesen, E., Nielsen, S.-H., Toth, L., Madsen, C., Pedersen, L., Poulsen, N., Kidmose, U., Larsen, L., Hebelstrup, K., 2024. Wheat bread making (WBM)-like Seed Proteins: a new family of small prolamins in barley. *J. Cereal. Sci.* 103961.
- Aziz, I., Lewis, N.R., Hadjivassiliou, M., Winfield, S.N., Rugg, N., Kelsall, A., Newrick, L., Sanders, D.S., 2014. A UK study assessing the population prevalence of self-reported gluten sensitivity and referral characteristics to secondary care. *Eur. J. Gastroenterol. Hepatol.* 26 (1), 33–39.
- Balakireva, A., Zamyatnin, A., 2016. Properties of gluten intolerance: gluten structure, evolution, pathogenicity and detoxification capabilities. *Nutrients* 8 (10), 644. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nu8100644>.
- Baxter, E.D., Wainwright, T., 1979. Hordein and malting Quality1. *J. Am. Soc. Brew. Chem.* 37 (1), 8–12. <https://doi.org/10.1094/ASBCJ-37-0008>.
- Benlier, N., Sayin, S., Cetin, Z., Ozkur, M., Saygili, E.I., 2021. Dietary fibers/beta-glucan and cancer. In: *Nutraceuticals and Cancer Signaling*. Springer International Publishing, pp. 569–590. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-74035-1_21.
- Besser, H.A., Khosla, C., 2023. Celiac disease: mechanisms and emerging therapeutics. *Trends Pharmacol. Sci.* 44 (12), 949–962. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tips.2023.09.006>.
- Blake, T.K., Ullrich, S.E., Nilan, R.A., 1982. Mapping of the hor-3 locus encoding D hordein in barley. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 63 (4), 367–371. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00303909>.
- Bobalova, J., Strouhalova, D., Bobal, P., 2023. Common post-translational modifications (PTMs) of proteins: analysis by up-to-date analytical techniques with an emphasis on barley. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 71 (41), 14825–14837. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.3c00886>.
- Bose, U., Broadbent, J.A., Byrne, K., Blundell, M.J., Howitt, C.A., Colgrave, M.L., 2020. Proteome analysis of hordein-null barley lines reveals storage protein synthesis and compensation mechanisms. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 68 (20), 5763–5775. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jafc.0c01410>.
- Bose, U., Juhász, A., Yu, R., Bahmani, M., Byrne, K., Blundell, M., Broadbent, J.A., Howitt, C.A., Colgrave, M.L., 2021. Proteome and nutritional shifts observed in hordein double-mutant barley lines. *Front. Plant Sci.* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpls.2021.718504>.
- Bradauskienė, V., Vaiciulytė-Funk, L., Martinaitienė, D., Andruskiene, J., Verma, A.K., Lima, J.P.M., Serin, Y., Catassi, C., 2023. Wheat consumption and prevalence of celiac disease: correlation from a multilevel analysis. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 63 (1), 18–32. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2021.1939650>.
- Brennan, C.S., Smith, D.B., Harris, N., Shewry, P.R., 1998. The production and characterisation of Hor 3 null lines of barley provides new information on the relationship of D hordein to malting performance. *J. Cereal. Sci.* 28 (3), 291–299. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0733-5210\(98\)90009-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0733-5210(98)90009-1).
- Camarca, A., Rotondi Aufiero, V., Mazzarella, G., 2023. Role of regulatory T cells and their potential therapeutic applications in celiac disease. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 24 (19), 14434. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms241914434>.
- Cameron-Mills, V., Brandt, A., 1988. A ?-hordein gene. *Plant Mol. Biol.* 11 (4), 449–461. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00039026>.
- Cameron-Mills, V., Von Wettstein, D., 1980. Protein body formation in the developing barley endosperm. *Carlsberg Res. Commun.* 45 (6), 577. <https://doi.org/10.1007/Bf02932924>.
- Colgrave, M.L., Byrne, K., Blundell, M., Heidelberger, S., Lane, C.S., Tanner, G.J., Howitt, C.A., 2016. Comparing multiple reaction monitoring and sequential window acquisition of all theoretical mass spectra for the relative quantification of barley gluten in selectively bred barley lines. *Anal. Chem.* 88 (18), 9127–9135. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.analchem.6b02108>.
- Cook, F., Hughes, A., Nibau, C., Orman-Ligeza, B., Schatlowski, N., Uauy, C., Trafford, K., 2018. Barley lys3 mutants are unique amongst shrunken-endosperm mutants in having abnormally large embryos. *J. Cereal. Sci.* 82, 16–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2018.04.013>.
- Dhingra, S., Jood, S., 2004. Effect of flour blending on functional, baking and organoleptic characteristics of bread. *Int. J. Food Sci. Technol.* 39 (2), 213–222. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.0950-5423.2003.00766.x>.
- Dieckman, T., Koning, F., Bouma, G., 2022. Celiac disease: new therapies on the horizon. *Curr. Opin. Pharmacol.* 66, 102268.
- Discepolo, V., Kelly, C.P., Koning, F., Schuppan, D., 2024. How future pharmacologic therapies for celiac disease will complement the gluten-free diet. *Gastroenterology* 167 (1), 90–103.
- Doil, H., 1980. A nearly non-functional mutant allele of the storage protein locus Hor2 in barley. *Hereditas* 93 (2), 217–222. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-3113.1980.tb010002.x>.
- Durrant, M.G., Perry, N.T., Pai, J.J., Jangid, A.R., Athukoralage, J.S., Hiraizumi, M., McSpedon, J.P., Pawluk, A., Nishimasu, H., Konermann, S., Hsu, P.D., 2024. Bridge RNAs direct programmable recombination of target and donor DNA. *Nature* 630 (8018), 984–993. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07552-4>.
- FAOSTAT, 2022. Faostat : crops and livestock products. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations. Retrieved 13-02-2022 from. <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL>.
- Farag, M.A., Xiao, J., Abdallah, H.M., 2022. Nutritional value of barley cereal and better opportunities for its processing as a value-added food: a comprehensive review. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 62 (4), 1092–1104. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2020.1835817>.
- Ferrari, B., Baronchelli, M., Stanca, A.M., Gianinetti, A., 2010. Constitutive differences between steely and mealy barley samples associated with endosperm modification. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 90 (12), 2105–2113. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsfa.4058>.

- Freddy, B.O., Aimé, D.N., Jacques, L.N.B., Sébastien, L.N., 2022. In: *Cisgenesis and Plant Breeding: A Review*. Springer International Publishing, pp. 79–87. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-06628-3_5.
- Gaj, T., Gersbach, C.A., Barbas, C.F., 2013. ZFN, TALEN, and CRISPR/Cas-based methods for genome engineering. *Trends Biotechnol.* 31 (7), 397–405. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2013.04.004>.
- Garvin, D.F., Brown, A.H.D., Raman, H., Read, B.J., 2000. Genetic mapping of the barley *Rrs14* scald resistance gene with RFLP, isozyme and seed storage protein markers. *Plant Breed.* 119 (3), 193–196. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1439-0523.2000.00456.x>.
- Grewal, T.S., Rossnagel, B.G., Scoles, G.J., 2004. Mapping of a covered smut resistance gene in barley (*Hordeum vulgare*). *J. Indian Dent. Assoc.* 26 (2), 156–166. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07060660409507127>.
- Grewal, T.S., Rossnagel, B.G., Scoles, G.J., 2007. Validation of molecular markers for covered smut resistance and marker-assisted introgression of loose and covered smut resistance into hullless barley. *Mol. Breed.* 21 (1), 37–48. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11032-007-9107-9>.
- Gu, Y.Q., Anderson, O.D., Londeoré, C.F., Kong, X., Chibbar, R.N., Lazo, G.R., 2003. Structural organization of the barley D-hordein locus in comparison with its orthologous regions of wheat genomes. *Genome* 46 (6), 1084–1097. <https://doi.org/10.1139/g03-071>.
- Hajjari, M.M., Sharif, N., 2024. Prolamins' 3D structure: A new insight into protein modeling using the language of numbers and shapes. *Food Hydrocolloids* 154, 110154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodhyd.2024.110154>.
- Han, Z., Wu, F., Deng, G., Qian, G., Yu, M., Jia, Y., 2010. Structural and expression analysis of the B-hordein genes in Tibetan hull-less barley. *Genetica* 138 (2), 227–239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10709-009-9415-6>.
- Hansen, M., Lange, M., Friis, C., Dionisio, G., Holm, P.B., Vincze, E., 2007. Antisense-mediated suppression of C-hordein biosynthesis in the barley grain results in correlated changes in the transcriptome, protein profile, and amino acid composition. *J. Exp. Bot.* 58 (14), 3987–3995. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxb/erm254>.
- Hardy, M.Y., Tye-Din, J.A., Stewart, J.A., Schmitz, F., Dudek, N.L., Hanchapala, I., Purcell, A.W., Anderson, R.P., 2015. Ingestion of oats and barley in patients with celiac disease mobilizes cross-reactive T cells activated by avenin peptides and immuno-dominant hordein peptides. *J. Autoimmun.* 56, 56–65. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaut.2014.10.003>.
- Hiraizumi, M., Perry, N.T., Durrant, M.G., Soma, T., Nagahata, N., Okazaki, S., Athukorralage, J.S., Isayama, Y., Pai, J.J., Pawluk, A., Konermann, S., Yamashita, K., Hsu, P.D., Nishimatsu, H., 2024. Structural mechanism of bridge RNA-guided recombination. *Nature* 630 (8018), 994–1002. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-07570-2>.
- Howard, K.A., Gayler, K.R., Eagles, H.A., Halloran, G.M., 1996. The relationship between D hordein and malting quality in barley. *J. Cereal. Sci.* 24 (1), 47–53. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jcrs.1996.0036>.
- Howitt, C.A., Larkin, P.J., Colgrave, M.L., 2018. Gluten reduction strategies for wheat and barley. *Cereal Foods World* 63 (5), 184–187. <https://doi.org/10.1094/Cfw-63-5-0184>.
- Izydorczyk, M.S., Edney, M., 2017. Barley: grain-quality characteristics and management of quality requirements. In: *Cereal Grains*. Elsevier, pp. 195–234.
- Jansson-Knodell, C.L., White, M., Lockett, C., Xu, H., Rubio-Tapia, A., Shin, A., 2023. Self-reported gluten intolerance is prevalent, but not all gluten-containing foods are equal. *Dig. Dis. Sci.* 68 (4), 1364–1368. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10620-022-07800-5>.
- Klemsdal, S.S., Kvaale, A., Olsen, O.A., 1986. Effects of the barley mutants Risø 1508 and 527 high lysine genes on the cellular development of the endosperm. *Physiol. Plantarum* 67 (3), 453–459. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1399-3054.1986.tb05762.x>.
- Koning, F., Gilissen, L., Wijmenga, C., 2005. Gluten: a two-edged sword. *Immunopathogenesis of celiac disease*. Springer Seminars in Immunopathology 27 (2), 217–232. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00281-005-0203-9>.
- Kreis, M., Rahman, S., Forde, B., Pywell, J., Shewry, P., Mifflin, B., 1983a. Sub-families of hordein mRNA encoded at the *Hor 2* locus of barley. *Mol. Gen. Genet.* MGG 191, 194–200.
- Kreis, M., Shewry, P., Forde, B., Rahman, S., Mifflin, B., 1983b. Molecular analysis of a mutation conferring the high-lysine phenotype on the grain of barley (*Hordeum vulgare*). *Cell* 34 (1), 161–167.
- Kreis, M., Shewry, P.R., Forde, B.G., Rahman, S., Mifflin, B.J., 1983c. Molecular analysis of a mutation conferring the high-lysine phenotype on the grain of barley (*Hordeum vulgare*). *Cell* 34 (1), 161–167. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-8674\(83\)90146-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0092-8674(83)90146-0).
- Kumar, V., Chaturvedi, S.K., Singh, G.P., 2023. Brief review of malting quality and frontier areas in barley. *Cereal Res. Commun.* 51 (1), 45–59. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42976-022-00292-z>.
- Lange, M., Vincze, E., Wieser, H., Schjoerring, J.K., Holm, P.B., 2007. Suppression of C-hordein synthesis in barley by antisense constructs results in a more balanced amino acid composition. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 55 (15), 6074–6081. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jf0709505>.
- Lexhaller, B., Ludwig, C., Scherf, K.A., 2020. Identification of isopeptides between human tissue transglutaminase and wheat, rye, and barley gluten peptides. *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-64143-9>.
- Li, Y., Liu, D., Zong, Y., Jiang, L., Xi, X., Cao, D., Shen, Y., Zhang, H., Liu, B., 2020. New D hordein alleles were created in barley using CRISPR/Cas9 genome editing. *Cereal Res. Commun.* 48 (2), 131–138. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42976-020-00023-2>.
- Lin, Q., Jin, S., Zong, Y., Yu, H., Zhu, Z., Liu, G., Kou, L., Wang, Y., Qiu, J.-L., Li, J., Gao, C., 2021. High-efficiency prime editing with optimized, paired pegRNAs in plants. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 39 (8), 923–927. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41587-021-00868-w>.
- Lin, Q., Zong, Y., Xue, C., Wang, S., Jin, S., Zhu, Z., Wang, Y., Anzalone, A.V., Raguram, A., Doman, J.L., 2020. Prime genome editing in rice and wheat. *Nat. Biotechnol.* 38 (5), 582–585.
- Lukinac, J., Jukic, M., 2022. Barley in the production of cereal-based products. *Plants* 11 (24). <https://doi.org/10.3390/plants11243519>.
- Maret, W., 2005. Zinc coordination environments in proteins determine zinc functions. *J. Trace Elem. Med. Biol.* 19 (1), 7–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jtemb.2005.02.003>.
- Michalek, W., Kleine, M., Dargatz, H., Wenzel, G., Jahoor, A., 1997. Stability of Hor1-specific YAC-clones and physical mapping of Hor1-loci in barley. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 95, 369–374.
- Mohammed, J., Seleshe, S., Nega, F., Lee, M., 2016. Revisit to Ethiopian traditional barley-based food. *Journal of Ethnic Foods* 3 (2), 135–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jef.2016.06.001>.
- Molina-Cano, J.L., Polo, J.P., Sopena, A., Voltas, J., Pérez-Vendrell, A.M., Romagosa, I., 2000. Mechanisms of malt extract development in barleys from different European regions: II. effect of barley hordein fractions on malt extract yield. *J. Inst. Brew.* 106 (2), 117–123. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2050-0416.2000.tb00048.x>.
- Newman, C.W., Øverland, M., Newman, R.K., Bang-Olsen, K., Pedersen, B., 1990. Protein quality of a new high-lysine barley derived from risø 1508. *Can. J. Anim. Sci.* 70 (1), 279–285. <https://doi.org/10.4141/cjas90-033>.
- Noori, E., Hashemi, N., Rezaee, D., Maleki, R., Shams, F., Kazemi, B., Bandepour, M., Rahimi, F., 2024. Potential therapeutic options for celiac disease: an update on Current evidence from Gluten-Free diet to cell therapy. *Int. Immunopharm.* 133, 112020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intimp.2024.112020>.
- Okura, Y., Ikawa-Teranishi, Y., Mizoroki, A., Takahashi, N., Tsushima, T., Irie, M., Harfuddin, Z., Miura-Okuda, M., Ito, S., Nakamura, G., Takesue, H., Ozono, Y., Nishihara, M., Yamada, K., Gan, S.W., Hayasaka, A., Ishii, S., Wakabayashi, T., Muraoka, M., Igawa, T., 2023. Characterizations of a neutralizing antibody broadly reactive to multiple gluten peptide:HLA-DQ2.5 complexes in the context of celiac disease. *Nat. Commun.* 14 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-023-44083-4>.
- Otero, E.A., Miralles, D.J., Peton, A., Conti, V.A., Giménez, F.J., Benech-Arnold, R.L., 2021. On-field assessment of the environmental modulation of malting quality in barley crops. *Field Crops Res.* 271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fcr.2021.108252>.
- Pedersen, C., Linde-Laursen, I., 1995. The relationship between physical and genetic distances at the *Hor1* and *Hor2* loci of barley estimated by two-colour fluorescent in situ hybridization. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 91 (6), 941–946. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00223904>.
- Picariello, G., Bonomi, F., Iametti, S., Rasmussen, P., Pepe, C., Lilla, S., Ferranti, P., 2011. Proteomic and peptidomic characterisation of beer: immunological and technological implications. *Food Chem.* 124 (4), 1718–1726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2010.07.111>.
- Pistón, F., Martín, A., Dorado, G., Barro, F., 2005. Cloning and molecular characterization of B-hordeins from *Hordeum chilense* (Roem. et Schult.). *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 111 (3), 551–560. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00122-005-2046-0>.
- Pomortsev, A.A., Rubanovich, A.V., Lialina, E.V., 2021. Structure and formation mechanisms of polymorphism of hordein-coding loci in domesticated barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). *Russ. J. Genet.* 57 (5), 548–560. <https://doi.org/10.1134/s1022795421050082>.
- Pomortsev, A.A., Rubanovich, A.V., Lyalina, E.V., 2022. The polymorphism structure of hordeins encoded by the *hrd A* and *hrd B* loci in wild barley (*Hordeum spontaneum* C. Koch.). *Russ. J. Genet.* 58 (3), 265–295. <https://doi.org/10.1134/s1022795422030115>.
- Prystupa, P., Peton, A., Pagano, E., Ferraris, G., Ventimiglia, L., Loewy, T., Gómez, F., Gutierrez-Boem, F.H., 2021. Grain hordein content and malt quality as affected by foliar nitrogen fertilisation at heading. *J. Inst. Brew.* 127 (3), 224–231. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jib.662>.
- Prystupa, P., Peton, A., Pagano, E., Gutierrez-Boem, F.H.G., 2019. Sulphur fertilization of barley crops improves malt extract and fermentability. *J. Cereal. Sci.* 85, 228–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2018.12.014>.
- Raj, R., Shams, R., Pandey, V.K., Dash, K.K., Singh, P., Bashir, O., 2023. Barley phytochemicals and health promoting benefits: a comprehensive review. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Research* 14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jafr.2023.100677>.
- Ran, F.A., Hsu, P.D., Lin, C.Y., Gootenberg, J.S., Konermann, S., Trevino, A.E., Scott, D.A., Inoue, A., Matoba, S., Zhang, Y., Zhang, F., 2013. Double nicking by RNA-guided CRISPR Cas9 for enhanced genome editing specificity. *Cell* 154 (6), 1380–1389. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2013.08.021>.
- Rej, A., Aziz, I., Sanders, D.S., 2020. Coeliac disease and noncoeliac wheat or gluten sensitivity. *J. Intern. Med.* 288 (5), 537–549. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joim.13120>.
- Ren, Q., Sretenovic, S., Liu, S., Tang, X., Huang, L., He, Y., Liu, L., Guo, Y., Zhong, Z., Liu, G., 2021. PAM-less plant genome editing using a CRISPR–SpRY toolbox. *Nat. Plants* 7 (1), 25–33. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41477-020-00827-4>.
- Roustan, V., Hilscher, J., Weidinger, M., Reipert, S., Shabrangy, A., Gebert, C., Dietrich, B., Dermendjiev, G., Schnurer, M., Roustan, P.J., Stoger, E., Ibl, V., 2020. Protein sorting into protein bodies during barley endosperm development is putatively regulated by cytoskeleton members, MVBs and the HvSNF7s. *Sci. Rep.* 10 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-58740-x>.
- Rubin, J.E., Crowe, S.E., 2020. Celiac disease. *Ann. Intern. Med.* 172 (1), ITC1–ITC16. <https://doi.org/10.7326/AITC202001070>.
- Rybalka, O.I., Katrii, V.B., Polishchuk, S.S., Morgun, B.V., 2021. Development of hull-less barley with ultra-low gluten content via target genes combination. I. Isolation of triple mutants and black grained genotypes. *Agricultural Science and Practice* 8 (1), 47–57. <https://doi.org/10.15407/agrisp8.01.047>.

- Schalk, K., Lexhaller, B., Koehler, P., Scherf, K.A., 2017. Isolation and characterization of gluten protein types from wheat, rye, barley and oats for use as reference materials. *PLoS One* 12 (2), e0172819. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0172819>.
- Scherf, K.A., 2023. In: *Gluten Proteins*. Elsevier, pp. 71–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-323-95295-8.00041-1>.
- Schmidt, M., 2022. Cereal beta-glucans: an underutilized health endorsing food ingredient. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 62 (12), 3281–3300. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2020.1864619>.
- Sharma, R., Mokhtari, S., Jafari, S.M., Sharma, S., 2022. Barley-based probiotic food mixture: health effects and future prospects. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 62 (29), 7961–7975. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2021.1921692>.
- Shewry, P., 2019. What is gluten—why is it special? *Front. Nutr.* 6, 101.
- Shewry, P., Bunce, N., Kreis, M., Forde, B., 1985a. Polymorphism at the Hor 1 locus of barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.). *Biochem. Genet.* 23, 391–404.
- Shewry, P., Faulks, A.J., Pickering, R., Jones, I., Finch, R., Mifflin, B., 1980a. The genetic analysis of barley storage proteins. *Heredity* 44 (3), 383–389.
- Shewry, P., Parmar, S., 1987. The HrdF (Hor 5) locus encodes gamma-type hordeins. *Barley Genet. Newsl.* 17, 32–34.
- Shewry, P.R., Faulks, A.J., Mifflin, B.J., 1980b. Effect of high-lysine mutations on the protein-fractions of barley-grain. *Biochem. Genet.* 18 (1–2), 133–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/Bf00504365>.
- Shewry, P.R., Faulks, A.J., Parmar, S., Mifflin, B.J., 1980c. Hordein polypeptide pattern in relation to malting quality and the varietal identification of malted barley-grain. *J. Inst. Brew.* 86 (3), 138–141. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.2050-0416.1980.tb03974.x>.
- Shewry, P.R., Finch, R.A., Parmar, S., Franklin, J., Mifflin, B.J., 1983. Chromosomal location of HOR 3, A new locus governing storage proteins in barley. *Heredity* 50 (2), 179–189. <https://doi.org/10.1038/hdy.1983.19>.
- Shewry, P.R., Halford, N.G., 2002. Cereal seed storage proteins: structures, properties and role in grain utilization. *J. Exp. Bot.* 53 (370), 947–958. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jxbbot/53.370.947>.
- Shewry, P.R., Kreis, M., Parmar, S., Lew, E.J.L., Kasarda, D.D., 1985b. Identification of γ -type hordeins in barley. *FEBS Lett.* 190 (1), 61–64. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-5793\(85\)80427-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-5793(85)80427-0).
- Siddiquee, R., Pong, C.H., Hall, R.M., Ataide, S.F., 2024. A programmable seekRNA guides target selection by IS1111 and IS110 type insertion sequences. *Nat. Commun.* 15 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-49474-9>.
- Siedler, H., Graner, A., 1991. Construction of physical maps of the Hor1 locus of two barley cultivars by pulsed field gel electrophoresis. *Mol. Gen. Genet. MGG* 226 (1), 177–181.
- Simic, G., Sudar, R., Lalic, A., Jurkovic, Z., Horvat, D., Babic, D., 2007. Relationship between hordein proteins and malt quality in barley cultivars grown in Croatia. *Cereal Res. Commun.* 35 (3), 1487–1496. <https://doi.org/10.1556/Crc.35.2007.3.13>.
- Swarts, D.C., Jinek, M., 2019. Mechanistic insights into the cis- and trans-acting DNase activities of Cas12a. *Molecular cell* 73 (3), 589–600. e584.
- Tan, J., Zeng, D., Zhao, Y., Wang, Y., Liu, T., Li, S., Xue, Y., Luo, Y., Xie, X., Chen, L., 2022. PhieABEs: a PAM-less/free high-efficiency adenine base editor toolbox with wide target scope in plants. *Plant Biotechnol. J.* 20 (5), 934–943.
- Tanner, G.J., Blundell, M.J., Colgrave, M.L., Howitt, C.A., 2016a. Creation of the first ultra-low gluten barley (L.) for coeliac and gluten-intolerant populations. *Plant Biotechnol. J.* 14 (4), 1139–1150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pbi.12482>.
- Tanner, G.J., Blundell, M.J., Colgrave, M.L., Howitt, C.A., 2016b. Creation of the first ultra-low gluten barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) for coeliac and gluten-intolerant populations. *Plant Biotechnol. J.* 14 (4), 1139–1150. <https://doi.org/10.1111/pbi.12482>.
- Tatham, A.S., Shewry, P.R., 2012. The S-poor prolamins of wheat, barley and rye: revisited. *J. Cereal. Sci.* 55 (2), 79–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcs.2011.10.013>.
- Tester, R.F., Morrison, W.R., Schulman, A.H., 1993. Swelling and gelatinization of cereal starches. V. Risø mutants of Bomi and Carlsberg II barley cultivars. *J. Cereal. Sci.* 17 (1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jcs.1993.1001>.
- This, H., 2018. Who discovered the gluten and who discovered its production by lixivation? *Notes Académiques de l'Académie d'agriculture de France* (3), 1–11. <https://hal.science/hal-01852558>.
- Tok, K., Moulahoum, H., Kocadag Kocazorbaz, E., Zihnioglu, F., 2021. Bioactive peptides with multiple activities extracted from Barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.) grain protein hydrolysates: biochemical analysis and computational identification. *J. Food Process. Preserv.* 45 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1111/jfpp.15024>.
- Tosh, S.M., Bordenave, N., 2020. Emerging science on benefits of whole grain oat and barley and their soluble dietary fibers for heart health, glycemic response, and gut microbiota. *Nutr. Rev.* 78 (Suppl. ment 1), 13–20. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nutrit/nuz085>.
- Tye-Din, J.A., Stewart, J.A., Dromey, J.A., Beissbarth, T., Van Heel, D.A., Tatham, A., Henderson, K., Mannering, S.I., Gianfrani, C., Jewell, D.P., Hill, A.V.S., McCluskey, J., Rossjohn, J., Anderson, R.P., 2010. Comprehensive, quantitative mapping of T cell epitopes in gluten in celiac disease. *Sci. Transl. Med.* 2 (41). <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.3001012>, 41ra51–41ra51.
- Uddin, M.N., Kaczmarczyk, A., Vincze, E., 2014a. Effects of Zn fertilization on hordein transcripts at early developmental stage of barley grain and correlation with increased Zn concentration in the mature grain. *PLoS One* 9 (9). <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0108546>.
- Uddin, M.N., Nielsen, A.L.L., Vincze, E., 2014b. Zinc blotting assay for detection of zinc-binding prolamins in barley grain. *Cereal Chem.* 91 (3), 228–232. <https://doi.org/10.1094/Cchem-09-13-0175-N>.
- Upreti, R., Grando, S., Macpherson, H.G., 2005. Status of Food Barley in Nepal.
- Vader, L.W., Stepniak, D.T., Bunnik, E.M., Kooy, Y.M.C., De Haan, W., Drijfhout, J.W., Van Veelen, P.A., Koning, F., 2003. Characterization of cereal toxicity for celiac disease patients based on protein homology in grains 1 The authors thank Drs. R. R. P. de Vries and R. Offringa for critical reading of the manuscript, A. de Ru for mass spectrometric analysis, and W. Benckh. *Gastroenterology* 125 (4), 1105–1113. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0016-5085\(03\)01204-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0016-5085(03)01204-6).
- Verma, R.P.S., Lal, C., Malik, R., Kharub, A.S., Kumar, L., Kumar, D., 2022. Barley improvement: current status and future prospects in changing scenario. In: Kashyap, P.L., Gupta, V., Prakash Gupta, O., Sendhil, R., Gopalareddy, K., Jasrotia, P., Singh, G.P. (Eds.), *New Horizons in Wheat and Barley Research: Global Trends, Breeding and Quality Enhancement*. Springer, Singapore, pp. 93–134. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-4449-8_6.
- Vinje, M.A., Gartman, L.S., Simmons, C.H., 2024. Characterization of a Near Isogenic Barley Line with High Grain B-Amylase Activity Reveals a Separation in the Tight Co-regulation of B-Hordeins (Hor2) with Endosperm-specific B-Amylase (Bmy1). Elsevier BV. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4851034>.
- Vinje, M.A., Simmons, C.H., 2024. Characterization of barley (*Hordeum vulgare*) lys3 mutants identifies genes under the regulation of the prolamins-box binding transcription factor and elucidates its role in endosperm promoter methylation during grain development. *Mol. Genet. Genom.* 299 (1). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00438-024-02112-x>.
- Vinje, M.A., Walling, J.G., Henson, C.A., Duke, S.H., 2019. Comparative gene expression analysis of the β -amylase and hordein gene families in the developing barley grain. *Gene* 693, 127–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gene.2018.12.041>.
- Wei, Y., Yang, Z., Zong, C., Wang, B., Ge, X., Tan, X., Liu, X., Tao, Z., Wang, P., Ma, C., 2021. Trans single-stranded DNA cleavage via CRISPR/Cas14a1 activated by target RNA without destruction. *Angew. Chem.* 133 (45), 24443–24449.
- Xu, J.H., Messing, J., 2009. Amplification of prolamins storage protein genes in different subfamilies of the Poaceae. *Theoretical and Applied Genetics* 119 (8), 1397–1412. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00122-009-1143-x>.
- Yang, Q., Zhong, X., Li, Q., Lan, J., Tang, H., Qi, P., Ma, J., Wang, J., Chen, G., Pu, Z., Li, W., Lan, X., Deng, M., Harwood, W., Li, Z., Wei, Y., Zheng, Y., Jiang, Q., 2020. Mutation of the d-hordein gene by RNA-guided Cas9 targeted editing reducing the grain size and changing grain compositions in barley. *Food Chem.* 311, 125892. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodchem.2019.125892>.
- Yang, S., Zhang, Y., Xu, J., Zhang, J., Zhang, J., Yang, J., Jiang, Y., Yang, S., 2021. Orthogonal CRISPR-associated transposases for parallel and multiplexed chromosomal integration. *Nucleic acids research* 49 (17), 10192–10202. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/gkab752>.
- Zhang, J., Deng, H., Bai, J., Zhou, X., Zhao, Y., Zhu, Y., McClements, D.J., Xiao, X., Sun, Q., 2023. Health-promoting properties of barley: a review of nutrient and nutraceutical composition, functionality, bioprocessing, and health benefits. *Crit. Rev. Food Sci. Nutr.* 63 (9), 1155–1169. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408398.2021.1972926>.
- Zheng, Q.N., Wang, Z., Xiong, F.Y., Song, Y., Zhang, G.Q., 2023. Effect of pearling on nutritional value of highland barley flour and processing characteristics of noodles. *Food Chem. X*, 17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fochx.2023.100596>.
- Zurbau, A., Noronha, J.C., Khan, T.A., Sievenpiper, J.L., Wolever, T.M.S., 2021. The effect of oat β -glucan on postprandial blood glucose and insulin responses: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur. J. Clin. Nutr.* 75 (11), 1540–1554. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41430-021-00875-9>.